

Comptes quotidiens en espèces du *bayt māl* (Trésor)
de Tūkar (Soudan) pour le mois de *dhū al-qaʿda* 1307.
Translittération

Enregistrement comptable quotidien des entrées et sorties en espèces du *bayt māl* de Tūkar, l'administration provinciale de l'État mahdiste au Soudan-Est.

Datation : ap. *dhū al-qaʿda* 1307 (approximativement) (juin-juillet 1890)

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Les pages 28 à 50 de ce manuscrit sont translittérées ci-dessous.

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Bi-smi-llāh al-raḥmān al-raḥīm wa ba‘ad fa-hadhā yawmiyyat al-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa bi-l-naqdiyya shahr al-qa‘da 1307 wa ‘alā Allāh al-tawfiq

yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak ghurra al-qa‘da 1307

al-jumla

0 r. 0 q. / ‘an al-muta’akhhir li-ghāyat shawwāl 1307

min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh / nimra 105

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-ma’khūdhā min Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh min rāyat Muḥammad al-Azraq ~~‘an yad~~ salafiyya ‘an yad al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna bi-ribāṭ Kasalā li-ḍarūrat tashīlāt al-katā’ib al-muḥaḍḍara min hinā li-hadhā al-ṭaraf kamā al-mukātaba al-wārīda min al-mukarram ‘Uthmān raqm 22 sha‘bān 1307 wa sharaḥa al-mukarram Majdhūb Abū Bakr ‘alay-hā raqm 7 al-qa‘da 1307 bi-‘alāwat al-mablagh bi-sm al-madhkūr wa ‘alā dhālika ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hi qūshlī / 1

80 r.

min ḥisāb maṣrūfāt rūk al-rāyāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāsil al-naqdiyya / nimra 131

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-muḥaḍḍara ‘an yad ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna bi-jihat Kasalā li-madhkūrīn min rūk al-rāyāt li-luzūm ṣarf-hā li-tashīlāt al-anṣār al-muḥaddara min-hā kamā al-ifāda al-wārīda min-hi raqm 22 sha‘bān 1307 al-dālla bi-dhālika wa sharaḥa al-mukarram Majdhūb Abū Bakr raqm 7 al-qa‘da wa ‘alā mawjibi-hi ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 2

80 r.

yawm al-arba‘ al-mubārak 7 dhū al-qa‘da 1307

min ḥisāb ḥāsil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisābat madhkūra

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥassila min mahdkūrīn wa muqaddama bi-ḥāfiẓ min-him wa idhn ṣādir li-amīn al-naqdiyya bi-l-qubūl wa sanad iḍāfa bi-khatm amīn al-naqdiyya wa ‘alā mawjibi-hi ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 3

110 r. / **ilā ḥisāb ‘ushr al-baḍā’i‘ al-tijāriyya** / jamī‘-hu ‘an-mā ṣāra muḥāsibat bi-hi Ādam Sālim al-Maṣūwa‘ī bi-Adūbana

ilā ḥisāb zakawāt al-naqdiyya / jamī‘-hu ‘an al-mutaḥaṣṣil min Ādam Sālim al-Maṣūwa‘ī zakāt nuqūdi-hi

9 r. 18 q. / zakāt mablagh 391 r. / 1305

7 r. / zakāt mablagh 281 r. / 1306

5 r. 18 q. / zakāt mablagh 227 r. / 1307

22 r. 12 q.

204 r. 12 q. / **ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb Aḥmad al-Ṣabbāgh** / jamīʿ-hu ʿan mā šara akhadh min-hi salafiyya li-ḍarūrat al-luzūm / nimra 70

337 r.

min ḥisāb al-maṭlūbāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāsil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa ilā Ādam Muḥammad Sālim al-Mašūwaʿī min maṭlūb al-mamlā bayt al-māl al-mamlā bayt al-māl li-muqṭadā idhn ṣādir li-amīn al-naqdiyya bi-l-ṣarf wa sanada bi-khatm istilām min ʿAbd Allāh Ādam Sālim al-madhkūr wa ʿalā mawjibi-ha ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fi taʾrīkhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / 4

337 r.

yawm al-sabt al-mubārak 10 dhū al-qaʿda 1307

min ḥisāb ḥāsil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ / nimra 106

834 r. 0 q.

naql baʿadi-hi bi-[waṣl] nimra 29

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tābiʿ yawm 10 dhū al-qaʿda 1307

tābiʿ al-jumla

834 r. 0 q.

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya qīmat thaman ādamiyya tusammā Baraka mushallakha balādī marbūʿ al-qāma shaʿr-hā [sātir] [sālimat] al-sunūn kāsir masbūq wujūda-hā ḥamīla bi-maʿrifat al-mukarram Abī Qarja wa kāna uḍifat ʿala ḥāsil al-raḥīq wa ubīʿat bi-mablagh 18 riyāl ilā Muḥammad Ḥusayn ʿAnnān wa wurida thaman-hā bi-ḥāsil al-naqdiyya wa [li-waʿy] Muḥammad ibn al-[Faḥīh] Ṣāliḥ al-madhkūr ʿalā ādamiyya wa istaḥaqqā-hā sharʿān wa li-muqṭadā mukātaba min Aḥmad Jābir nāʿib al-shariʿ fi 10 shawwāl 1307 wa min ḍimna mā ushira bi-hā [takūn] fi ṣarf al-mablagh li-l-madhkūr wa li-khulū bayt al-māl wa munāsabat al-qāʿida al-ḥisābiyya iqtadā al-ḥāl li-iḍāfat al-mablagh bi-ḥāsil al-naqdiyya ilā Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ muqābil al-ʿalāwa ṭalab bi-smi-hi li-muqṭadā idhn khaṣm wa iḍāfa fi taʾrīkhi-hi wa sayātī idhn khaṣm al-mablagh bi-ḥāsil al-maṣrūfāt bi-l-murtajaʿāt li-sadādi-hi / nimra 132 / 5

18 r.

min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt al-murtajaʿāt / ilā ḥisāb al-naqdiyya / nimra 132

wa dhālika ʿan qīmat thaman al-ādamiyya al-muwaḍḍaḥa bi-l-idhn qīl-hu al-[ṣādir] ʿan-hā mā amara nāʿib al-shariʿ minfi 10 shawwāl 1307 bi-rtijāʿ thaman-hā ilā mustaḥiqq-hā Muḥammad Sāliḥ li-sadd ḍiyāʿ-hā min-hi bi-[wajhi] al-

hamila al-masbūq mabī^ʿ-hā ilā Muḥammad Ḥusayn ʿAnnān wa [muḍiā]-hā wa li-
darūrat al-muwāzana taqaddama idhn idāfat al-mablagh ʿalā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya
wa li-darūrat sadād-hu bi-l-murtaja^ʿāt taḥarrara al-idhn al-lāzim fī taʾrikhi-hi / 6

18 r.

yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak 15 al-qaʿda 1307

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb ʿushr al-baḍāʾī^ʿ al-tijāriyya

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila min madhkūrīn qīmat a^ʿshār baḍāʾī^ʿ
al-muḥarrar bi-hā kashf wa sanad idāfa bi-khatm amīn al-naqdiyya al-sayyid
Aḥmad Ḥusayn wa ʿalā mawjibi-hi ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-
idāfa fi-taʾrikhi-hi / jamī^ʿ-hu qūshli / 7

bi-sm al-[?] ʿAbd Allāh

riyāl / ʿadad / fī riyāl

412 r. 12 q. / 7,5 / khām bi-l-kawraja wa 5 ṭāqa / 55 r.

64 r. / 4 / mushakkalāt bi-l-kawraja

105 r. / 6 / marmar bi-l-kawraja / 17 r. 12 q.

65 r. / 3,75 / rizāq bi-l-kawraja / 17 r. 12 q.

52 r. / 4 / ṣābūn bi-l-qanṭār / 13 r.

698 r. 12 q. / 25,25

70 r.

1 r. 12 q. / bi-sm Aḥmad Muḥammad / ʿushr dhura 18 q. / ʿushr ruz hindī
18 q. / aṣlu-hu 6

1 r. 6 q. / Ḥāmid ʿAlī Sharʿab / ʿushr dhura / aṣlu-hu 3

1 r. 12 q. / Ḥusayn ʿIsā al-Qarʿīb / ʿushr ruz hindī wa daqīq / aṣlu-hu 2

3 r. / ʿAlī Muḥammad Raḥmāy / ʿushsur ruz hindī / aṣlu-hu 5

1 r. / Ḥāmid ʿAlī Maḥallāwī / ʿushr ruz hindī / aṣlu-hu 2

3 r. / Ḥāmid ʿAlī / ʿushr ruz hindī / aṣlu-hu 2

2 r. / Ḥasan ʿAbd Allāh / ʿushr dhura / aṣlu-hu 5

1 r. / Ḥamad al-[Faqīh] / ʿushr dhura / aṣlu-hu 2

84 r. 6 q.

870 r.

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tābi^ʿ yawm 15 al-qaʿda 1307

870 r. / muwāṣala

tābi^ʿ min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

84 r. 6 q. / muwāṣala

3 r. 18 q. / ʿAbd al-Rāziq al-Ḥājj Aḥmad / ʿushr ruz hindī wa sukkar bi-l-
sandūq / aṣlu-hu 3

3 r. / Ḥāmid Muḥammad / ʿushr thiyāb mushakkala / aṣlu-hu 30
1 r. 18 q. / Ḥusayn Muḥammad / ʿushr ruz hindī / aṣlu-hu 3
18 q. / Muḥammad Dibalūb / ʿushr dhura / aṣlu-hu 2
1 r. 12 q. / Muḥammad Ḥamad min al-Ashrāf / ʿushr dhura kīs / aṣlu-hu 2
1 r. / Akram Ḥamad Nūrābī / ʿushr dhura kīs / aṣlu-hu 4
18 r. 3 q. / Sālim Sulaymān / ʿushr dhura 17 ruz hindī 17 / aṣlu-hu 34
7 r. 18 q. / Muḥammad Abū Zawīd / aṣlu-hu 2
1 r. / Muḥammad al-Qurayshī / ʿushr ruz hindī / aṣlu-hu 2
122 r. 21 q.

min hisāb al-naqdiyya / ilā hisāb al-zakawāt

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila min madhkūrīn qīmat zakawāt nuqūd-hum ʿām 1307 wa muwaḍḍaḥa bayān mufradāt-hum bi-daftar al-zakawāt ṭaraf amīn-hi al-Bashīr Aḥmad Ḥusayn kamā al-mukātiba al-wārida min-hi wa li-ḍarūrat idāfat al-mablagh ʿalā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya ʿuḥdat al-Bashīr qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-idāfa fī taʾrikhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / 8

7 r. 12 q.

yawm al-thalāth al-mubārak 20 al-qaʿda 1307

min hisāb al-naqdiyya / ilā hisāb mutaḥaṣṣilāt al-ʿushr bi-Adūbana

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila bayt māl Adūbana ʿan yad amīn-hā Aḥmad Muḥammad Maḥmūd wa munṣarif ʿan yadi-hi kamā al-kashf al-muqaddam min-hi bi-khāṭṭ Muḥammad Maḥmūd kātib li-jihati-hi wa khatm al-amīn al-madhkūr wa li-ḍarūrat idāfa ʿalā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya wa ṭabqān li-l-qāʿida ḥisābiyya qad ṣādir al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-idāfa fī taʾrikhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / 9

45 r. 3 q.

min hisāb al-maṣrūfāt / ilā hisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa bayt māl Adūbana ʿuḥdat Aḥmad Muḥammad Maḥmūd amīn li-jihati-hi wa muqaddama bi-kashf bi-khatm amīn bayt māl li-jihāti-hi Aḥmad Maḥmūd wa ʿalā mawjibi-him bi-[mumla] ʿan al-sunūd al-lāzima wa ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-idāfa fī taʾrikhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / 10

rāyat al-mukarram ʿUthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb / nimra 130

4 r. 12 q. / munṣarif li-madhkūrīn murattab-hum min 11 li-ghāyat 20 min-hi / 7 nafar / 4 nafar

2 r. 9 q. 1 qr. / munṣarif li-madhkūrīn murattab-hum min 11 jumāda awal li-ghāyat 20 min-hi / 3 nafar / 6 nafar

6 r. 21 q. 1 qr.

[crossed] Ḥasan Mūsā / nimra 96

3 r. / munşarîf li-madhkūrîn murattab-hum min ghurraṭ jumāda awal li-ghāyat 10 min-hi / 3 nafar / 6 nafar

1 r. / munşarîf ilā Muḥammad Maḥmūd [‘Ajṭalī] min murattabi-hi

4 r.

10 r. 21 q. 1 qr.

10 r. 21 q. 1 qr.

10 r. 21 q. 1 qr.

1045 r. 12 q.

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tābi‘ yawm 20 al-qa‘da 1307

tābi‘ al-jumla

1045 r. 12 q. / muwāşala

tābi‘ min hisāb al-maşrūfāt

10 r. 21 q. 1 qr. / muwāşala

rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ‘Uṭhmān Abī Qarja khāşşa / nimra 133

5 r. 12 q. / munşarîf li-madhkūrîn murattab-hum min ghurraṭ min-hi li-ghāyat 10 min-hi

12 r. 12 q. / munşarîf li-madhkūrîn jihādiyya murattab-hum min 11 min-hi li-ghāyat 20 min-hi / nafar 20 / nadar 10

3 r. 3 q. / munşarîf ilā Muḥammad Sirār luzūm musā‘ada li-l-ta’aşşul ṭibqa amr Abī Qarja

3 r. 6 q. 2 qr. / munşarîf ilā Muḥammad Ḥāmid murattab min ghurraṭ [nun] li-ghāyat 20 min-hi

2 r. / munşarîf ilā ‘Alī al-Ḥājj Aḥmad min murattabi-hi shahr ‘ām 1307

12 q. / munşarîf ilā Yūsuf ‘Alī al-Mardī

3 r. 18 q. / munşarîf ilā ‘Alī Aḥmad Taha badal 3 kīs murattab-hu shahr jumāda awal / bi-amr Majdhūb

3 r. / munşarîf li-madhkūrîn murattab-hum min 11 [nun] li-ghāyat sharh / nafar 3

12 q. / murattab nafar 1 min al-ta’rikhi qīl-hu li-ghāyat 20 min-hi / 1

34 r. 3 q. 2 qr.

45 r. 3 q.

min hisāb al-naqdiyya / ilā hisāb al-fuyūḍāt al-karīm

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaşşila ‘alā yad Muḥammad ‘Uṭhmān ‘Abd al-Raḥmān al-muqaddam bi-l-nuḡṭa al-mu‘adda li-l-muḥāfiz mā bayna al-marsā wa Tūkar wa munşarîfa ‘an yadi-hi wa li-ḍarūrat idāfati-hi ‘alā ḥāşil al-naqdiyya taṭbīqān li-l-qā‘ida al-ḥisābiyya qad şādara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaşm al-idāfa fi

ta'rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī' -hu qūshlī / 11

131 r. 3 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfat / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika 'an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifā 'an yad Muḥammad 'Uthmān 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-muqaddam bi-l-nuqṭa al-mu'adda li-l-muḥāfiz mā bayna al-marsā wa Tūkar kamā al-kashf al-muqaddam bi-khatmi-hi wa 'alā mawjibi-him ṣādara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-iḍāfa fī ta'rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī' -hu qūshlī / 12

khāṣṣa rāyat al-mukarram 'Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna / nimra 130

3 r. / munṣarif ilā Mūsā Nafal al-muqaddam badal murattab-hu min al-dhura [mā-hu] shahr

14 r. 21 q. 2 qr. / munṣarif li-madhkūrīn badal murattab-hum min al-dhura [mā-hu] shahr

5 r. / munṣarif ilā Mūsā Nafal al-muqaddam murattab-hu [mā-hu] shahr

15 r. / munṣarif li-madhkūrīn anṣār [mā-hu] shahr / nafar 10 / fī riyāl 1 r. 12 q.

37 r. 21 q. 2 qr.

rāyat Shā'ib Aḥmad Shaykh Faḍalū / nimra 127

8 r. 18 q. / munṣarif ilā Muḥammad 'Uthmān 'Abd al-Raḥmān murattab-hu shahr al-qa'da fī al-dhura

3 r. / munṣarif ilā Ibrāhīm Shaykh Khatar al-muqaddam badal murattab-hum min al-dhura [mā-hu] shahr

3 r. / munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Aḥmad Idrīs al-muqaddam murattab-hu [mā-hu] shahr badal al-dhura

26 r. 6 q. / 'an al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn badal murattab-hum min ṣanf al-ghilāl

10 r. / 'an al-munṣarif Muḥammad 'Uthmān 'Abd al-Raḥmān fī nazīr murattab-hu min al-nuqūd [mā-hu] shahr

5 r. / 'an al-munṣarif ilā Ibrāhīm Shaykh Khatar murattab-hu [mā-hu] shahr

5 r. / Muḥammad Aḥmad Idrīs / shuriḥa qīl-hu

7 r. 6 q. / qīmat thaman mayāh li-khadamā al-bi'r jarī

68 r. 6 q.

37 r. 21 q. 2 qr.

1221 r. 18 q.

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tābi' al-jumla

1221 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

tābi' yawm 20 al-qa'da 1307

tābi‘ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

37 r. 21 q. 2 qr. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ min rāyat Shā‘ib Aḥmad Shaykh Faḍalū

68 r. 6 q. / muwāṣala

12 r. 9 q. / munṣarif li-madhkūrīn 18 nafar munṣarif murattab-hum min al-nuqūd [mā-hu] shahr

2 r. 12 q. / qīmat ijār ādamīnīn li-ma‘kūl al-anṣār

6 r. / thaman mayāh li-khadamā al-bi‘r

1 r. 6 q. / ‘Abd al-Ḥalīm ‘Umar nazīr musā‘ada ‘alā al-[ta’aṣṣul]

1 r. / ‘Abd al-Ḥalīm Ḥāmid ḍarar

6 q. / Muḥammad ‘Uthmān al-ma‘adhdhin thaman sarwāl

1 r. 12 q. / ‘Abd al-Farāj thaman jubba wa sarwāl

93 r. 6 q. 1 qr.

131 r. 3 q.

yawm al-arba‘ al-mubārak 21 al-qa‘da

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb mutaḥaṣṣilāt al-‘ushr bi-Tūkar bi-l-marsā

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila ‘an yad Muḥammad Yūsuf amīn marsat al-Trinkītāt [mā-hu] shahr wa munṣarifa ‘an yadi-hi li-madhkūrīn li-muqtaḍā udhunāt ṣādira ilāy-hi bi-l-ṣarf wa muqaddama ṭayy ḥāfiẓa bi-khatmi-hi wa li-ḍarūrat idāfati-hā ‘alā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya taṭbīqān li-l-qā‘ida al-ḥisābiyya qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-idāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 13

1008 r. 3 q.

min ḥisāb madhkūrāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa ‘an yad Muḥammad Yūsuf amīn al-marsa fimā-hu shahr li-muqtaḍā ‘udhunāt ‘adad 166 ṣādira ilāy-hi bi-l-ṣarf wa muqaddamīn ṭayy ḥāfiẓa bi-khatm wa ‘ala mawjibi-hum ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm al-idāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 14

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt

iḥsānāt

rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

khāṣṣa rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna / nimra 129

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Ḥāmid al-mulāzim li-izālat ḍarar

25 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Amānī Muḥammad luzūm zuwwādat al-‘āmil ‘Uthmān min Kasalā li-Tūkar

2 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Idrīs Fādlābī li-mu‘ālaḥati-hi

28 r.

rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb / nimra 130

2 r. 12 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Karār Muḥammad Aḥmad wa Abū [Faldāy] thaman ṭāqat khām

15 q. 1 qr. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā al-Ḥasan Ṣadiq li-izālat ḍarar

7 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā ʿAbd Allāh Shamsī thaman qawjara tamr ma'khūdh min-hi li-manzil al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb

18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ʿAli Ḥamad ḍarar

7 r. / wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā al-Ṭayyib al-muqaddam al-muḥaddar min Kasalā bi-amr al-Majdhūb

17 r. 21 q. 1 qr.

28 r.

28 r.

2361 r. 0 q.

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2361 r. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ yawm 21 al-qaʿda 1307

tābiʿ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

tābiʿ al-iḥsānāt

tābiʿ rāyat al-mukarram ʿUthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

28 r. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb

178 r. 21 q. 1 qr. / muwāṣala

2 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā al-ʿArabī Aḥmad al-Ḥujjāj izālat ḍarar

5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Ḥusayn Khalil al-Hindī

ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

1 r. / Ḥāmid [Labībāy]

1 r. / Muḥammad ʿAbbās

6 q. / Aḥmad ʿAbd Allāh

12 q. / Akkad wa Khayr Allāh

2 r. 18 q.

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

4 r. / Al-Ḥasan Sadīq thaman sayf

3 r. / li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh Abū Bakr Yūsuf

2 r. 12 q. / Abū Fāṭima Abū [Falday]

9 r. 12 q.

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn thaman dhura

5 r. 6 q. / bi-yad Sabāḥ al-Khayr thaman dhura kīs 1 li-manzil [sayyid] al-Majdhūb Abū Bakr

15 r. 18 q. / bi-yad ʿAbd al-Karīm ʿAbd Allāh thaman dhura luzūm manāzil [sayyid]

21 r.

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn izālat ḍarar

3 r. / Akram ʿAlī

2 r. / Sūmīt ʿAbd Allāh

12 q. / Ḥusayn al-Maḥmūdāy

5 r. 12 q.

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

12 q. / Faḍl Allāh ʿAlī Yūsuf wa Farḥ Allāh al-Shukrī

12 q. / ḥarīmāt marḍā bi-dāʿ al-ḥalq wa hiya barīd wa [shaʿida]

1 r.

3 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Ḥāmid Sanūsī li-izālat ḍarar

14 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā ʿAbd Allāh Shamsī thaman ruz hindī kīs 2 maʿkhūdh min-hi ilā Marjān al-kāʿil

7 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Fāʿid Abū Bakr thaman kīs daqīq li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh Abū Bakr

7 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Ḥāmid [Labībāy] ḍarar

5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā ʿAbd al-Wāhid ʿAbd Allāh

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Yūsuf li-izālat ḍarar

2 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Marjān al-kāʿil izālat ḍarar

1 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Bakhīt al-Wāq wa Mabruk ʿAbd Allāh

107 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

rāyat Aḥmad al-Majdhūb / nimra 28

20 r. / wa sanad munṣarif ilā Ṭāhir Aḥmad al-Majdhūb li-sadād mā ʿalay-hi min al-duyūn

6 r. / wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Rāshid izālat ḍarar

26 r.

161 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

2361 r. 0 q.

161 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

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tābiʿ yawm 21 al-qaʿda 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābi‘ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

tābi‘ al-iḥsānāt

tābi‘ rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

161 r. 15 q. 1 qr. / muwāṣala

rāyat Muḥammad Muḥammad al-Azraq / nimra 12

1 r. 6 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Makkī Muḥammad al-Makkī
izālat ḍarar

1 r. / ḍimna idhn munṣarif ilā Aḥmad ‘Abd Allāh thaman bunn qahwa

12 q. / ḍimna idhn munṣarif ilā Kūkū al-Makkī

4 r. 6 q. / bi-dhni-hi ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Aḥmad ‘Abd Allāh min ḍimna
thaman jāriyya bi-amr al-Majdhūb

1 r. 18 q. / bi-dhn munṣarif li-l-madhkūrīn qīl-hu / shuriḥā

2 r. 6 q. / bi-dhn li-l-madhkūrīn qīl-hu / shuriḥā

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Nāfi‘ li-izālat ḍarar

12 r.

rāyat Faḍl ‘Abd Allāh / nimra 19

6 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā ‘Alī Ṣāliḥ li-sadād dīn-hi

3 r. 6 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Khūjalī al-Shaykh wa
Ḥāmid Mūsā izālat ḍarar

9 r. 6 q.

rāyat al-Ṭāhir Muḥammad ‘Alī Diqna / jamī‘-hu bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-
munṣarif li-maqādīm al-rāya / nimra 24

6 r. / [Fatawī] Muḥammad al-Amīn

5 r. 12 q. / ‘Abd al-Qādir Muḥammad al-Amīn

5 r. 12 q. / Akram Muḥammad

5 r. 12 q. / Khalīl Ibrāhīm

22 r. 12 q.

rāyat ‘Awḍ al-Karīm Kāfūt / nimra 95

8 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad
Aḥmad [Bala] bi-sm Majdhūb

1 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh luzūm
Aḥmad al-Bashīr

1 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā ‘Alī Faḍl al-Mūlā

6 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad al-Fakkāk

16 r. 12 q.

3 r. / rāyat ‘Alī Muḥammad al-‘Abādī / jamī‘-hu bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif
li-khāṣṣa ‘Alī al-‘Abādī li-izālat ḍarar / nimra 21

2 r. / rāyat Muṣṭafā ‘Alī Hadal / jamī‘-hu bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā
[Ḥamīd] Muḥammad izālat ḍarar / nimra 16

3 r. 12 q. / rāyat Banī ‘Āmir jamā‘at Muḥammad al-Ḥusayn / jamī‘-hu bi-
dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad al-Ḥusayn li-izālat ḍarar /
nimra 25

2 r. / rāyat [Shatīma] jamī‘-hu / bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munṣarif ilā
Ibrāhīm Jibrīl / nimra 18

232 r. 9 q. 1 qr.

rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ʿUthmān Abī Qarja

khāssat rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ʿUthmān Abī Qarja / nimra 133

12 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Faḍl ʿAlī li-izālat ḍarar

3 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Aḥmad Bābikar al-Jāz li-izālat ḍarar

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

19 r. / Ḥusayn ʿUthmān min ḍimna thaman jamal

7 r. / li-madhkūrīn jihādiyya

26 r.

5 r. 6 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Surūr al-amīn izālat ḍarar wa thaman khām

2 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā al-Ḥusayn Aḥmad

36 r. 18 q.

232 r. 96 q. 1 qr.

2361 r. 0 q.

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tābiʿ yawm 21 al-qaʿda 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ min ḥisābat madhkūra

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

tābiʿ al-iḥsānāt

232 r. 9 q. 1 qr. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ʿUthmān Abī Qarja

tābiʿ khāssat rāyat Abī Qarja

363 r. / muwāṣala

3 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Aḥmad ʿAbd Allāh wa Sūmīt maqādīm li-l-jihādiyya

1 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Ṭāhir ʿAlī li-izālat ḍarar

9 r. 3 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Faḍl ʿAlī thaman kīs dhura li-ʿawāʾilati-hi

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Aḥmad Jābir naʿib al-shariʿa li-izālat ḍarar

53 r. 21 q.

rāyat Yūsuf al-amīn al-Hindī / nimra 42

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ʿAbd al-Khāliq ʿAbd al-Qādir / thaman [musakkin] li-jamāʿat walad al-Hindī

6 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Maʿrūf izālat ḍarar

4 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Maryūd al-[Ṭarbinī] luzūm

jamā'at Abū al-Qāsim al-Mardī

13 r. 12 q.

rāyat Muḥammad 'Abd Allāh Fāna / nimra 122

2 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad 'Alī izālat ḍarar
15 q. 1 qr. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad 'Abd
Allāh Fāna thaman sukkar

4 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Ṭaha 'Umar li-izālat ḍarar

1 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Ibrāhīm 'Abd Allāh

3 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Ṭaha 'Umar li-izālat ḍarar

11 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

79 r. 1 qr.

1 r. 12 q. / khāṣṣat rāyat Shā'ib Aḥmad / jamī'-hu bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā
Ṣabbāgh muqaddam al-jihādiyya / nimra 128

1 r. / rāyat al-Ta'ā'isha / jamī'-hu bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Yūsuf Ṣāliḥ /
nimra 137

rāyat al-Sayyid Muḥammad Aḥmad al-Shaykh Idrīs / nimra 110

bi-sm Muḥammad 'Uthmān Ḥamad Tawm

2 r. 18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad

4 r. 18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ujrāt ḥamīr wa izālat ḍarar

4 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad thaman qawjara tamr

8 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad tanaka saman

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

22 r. 12 q.

9 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Abū 'Āqla 'Āqib bi-amr Majdhūb

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Muḥammad 'Uthmān
Ḥamad Tawm luzūm mawjib būṣ anṣār al-rāya

32 r. 12 q.

maṣrūfāt sā'ira

ḍuyūf / nimra 124 r.

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad ilā Muḥammad 'Abbās thaman bunn qahwa
luzūm al-ḍuyūf

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad bi-yad al-madhkūr qīl-hu / thaman miyāh
luzūm al-khadamā wa al-duyūf

2 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn [wāridīn] wa
[mutarridīn] / thaman miyāh wa [khīṭ] wa khashab

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā taḥassun ḍuyūf / thaman
miyāh li-madhkūrīn

4 r. 12 q.

346 r. 9 q. 2 qr.

2361 r. 0 q.

tābi' yawm 21 al-qa'da 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāṣala

tābi' min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābi' min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

tābi' al-iḥsānāt

346 r. 9 q. 2 qr. / muwāṣala

maṣrūfāt sā'ira

tābi' al-ḍuyūf

4 r. 12 q. / muwāṣala

bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif 'an yad [al-Ḥasan ṣarif]

12 q. / thaman bunn qahwa

4 r. 3 q. 1 qr. / thaman [?]

4 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn ḍuyūf

14 r. 12 q. / thaman kīs dhura

5 r. / maṣārīf [ḍarūriyya]

9 r. 12 q.

18 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

ajr jimāl / nimra 74

2 r. 12 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Mūsā Muḥammad /
ujrat jimāl fī mashāl dhura min al-marsā li-Tūkar

5 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā 'Umar Aḥmad [‘Āwalī] /
ujrat jimāl / shuriḥa

19 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Mūsā Maḥmūd muqaddam al-
jimāl ujrat mashāl al-‘uyūsh min al-marsā li-Tūkar

27 r.

2 r. / hajjāna al-būṣṭa / jamī' -hu ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā
Awshaykh 'Alī al-hajjān / nimra 123

aqlām sā'ira / nimra 131

12 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad 'an al-munṣarif ilā Karār Muḥammad /
thaman miyāh wa khulāma luzūm madhkūrīn

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā barīd wa [sha'īda] marḍā bi-dā'
al-ḥalq

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn thaman kafāna

3 r. / [Imān] 'Abd Allāh luzūm daqīq bayt al-māl

12 q. / Abū Faṭīma Abū [Falday] / thaman kafan

18 q. / Abū al-[Fataḥ] Mūsā Diqna / shuriḥa

1 r. / al-Amīn [Dīnbāy] / shuriḥa

12 q. / Muḥammad Idrīs / shuriḥa

1 r. 12 q. / Sabāḥ al-Khayr al-Majdhūb / shuriḥa

7 r. 6 q.

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Muḥammad ʿAbbās / thaman ḥalla nuḥāsī luzūm maʿkūl khadamā bayt al-māl wa thaman miyāh

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Mūsā Maḥmūd al-muḥaḍḍar min al-Qaqara

bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munşarif li-madhkūrīn

2 r. / Muḥammad Aḥmad al-muḥaḍḍar min Kasalā

2 r. / Muḥammad Rāshid / thaman waraq li-ʿamaliyyat al-kitāba wa ujrāt jamal

4 r.

9 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā hajjāna / thaman kafan

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Sharīf Muşţafā min Ashrāf [Baraka] li-izālat ḍarar

bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā madhkūrīn

1 r. / al-Makkī Muḥammad wa Faḍl ʿAlī / thaman miyāh

18 q. / luzūm ḥarīmāt marḍā bi-l-marsā

1 r. 18 q.

19 r. 9 q.

47 r. 15 q. 1 qr.

346 r. 9 q. 2 qr.

2361 r. 0 q.

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tābiʿ yawm 21 al-qaʿda 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāşala

tābiʿ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maşrūfāt

tābiʿ al-iḥsānāt

346 r. 9 q. 2 qr. / muwāşala

tābiʿ al-maşrūfāt al-sāʿira

48 r. 15 q. 1 qr. / muwāşala

tābiʿ al-aqlām al-sāʿira

19 r. 9 q. / muwāşala

2 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Ṭāhir [Qilāmī] izālat ḍarar

bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn

1 r. / thaman miyāh

1 r. / ḥarīmāt marad-hā bi-dāʿ al-ḥalq

2 r.

2 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad ʿan al-munşarif ilā Muḥammad ʿAbbās / thaman miyāh

- bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munşarif li-madhkūrīn khadamā bi-l-marsā
 1 r. / li-madhkūrīn khadamā bi-l-marsā / 12 nafar
 1 r. / li-ḥarīmāt mardā bi-dā’ al-ḥalq
 2 r. / awlād ‘arab khadamā bi-l-marsā
 4 r.
- bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munşarif li-madhkūrīn khadamā bi-l-marsā
 1 r. 12 q. / thaman miyāh ilā al-Makkī wa Maḥmūd Rāshid wa Muşţafā ‘Alī
 2 r. 12 q. / li-l-jihādiyya al-khadamā bi-l-marsā izālat ḍarar
 4 r.
- bi-dhn wa sanad ‘an al-munşarif li-madhkūrīn thaman miyāh
 1 r. / thaman miyāh li-l-jihādiyya
 3 r. / li-madhkūrīn ḍuyūf [wārida] wa [mizwada]
 12 q. / Aḥmad ‘Abd Allāh
 12 q. / Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh Fāna
 5 r.
- bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn thaman miyāh
 4 r. 6 q. / li-madhkūrīn jihādiyya khadamā bi-l-marsā
 2 r. / li-l-jihādiyya / nafar 10
 1 r. / li-madhlkūrīn abnā’ ‘arab
 1 r. / Aḥmad ‘Abd Allāh
 8 r. 6 q.
- 1 r. 18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn khadamā bi-l-marsā
 ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn
 1 r. 6 q. / Rizq Muḥammad
 1 r. / ḥarīmāt mardā bi-dā’ al-ḥalq
 2 r. 6 q.
- 51 r. 3 q.
 98 r. 18 q. 1 qr.
- 445 r. 6 q.
 mukāfa’āt / nimra [void]
 16 r. / munşarif Muḥammad al-Nūr amīn al-‘imāra murattab-hu shahrī jumāda akhar wa rajab / nimra 32
 19 r. 12 q. / Ḥasan Ādam al-[Tūfkajī] murattab jumāda akhar wa rajab / [?] nimra 24
 35 r. 12 q.
- 480 r. 18 q.
- 2361 r. 0 q.

tābi‘ yawm 21 al-qa‘da 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

480 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

min ḥisāb maṭlūb madhkūrīn

min maṭlūb ‘Abd al-Qādir Aḥmad Yaḥyā / nimra 84

5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

6 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa qīl-hu

3 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa

31 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

8 r. / shuriḥa

5 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad

8 r. / shuriḥa

10 r. / shuriḥa

20 r. / shuriḥa

97 r. 12 q.

10 r. / min maṭlūb Aḥmad Mayāh / nimra 49

min maṭlūb al-Sayyid Ḥusayn al-Ṣāfi / nimra 94

11 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

6 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad

5 r. 6 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad

23 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

12 r. / shuriḥa

1 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa

59 r. 6 q.

min maṭlūb Muḥammad Shākīr / nimra 94

22 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munāwala wakīl-hu ‘Abd Allāh [?]

1 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa qīl-hu

11 r. 6 q. / shuriḥa

20 r. / shuriḥa

55 r. 6 q.

min maṭlūb Shams al-Ruwayhī / nimra 51

15 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad

2 r. / shuriḥa

8 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa

26 r.

min maṭlūb Ṣāliḥ [ʿAdawī] al-[Ḥadāwab] / nimra 100

118 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

3 r. / shuriḥa

121 r.

min maṭlūb ʿUthmān [?] / nimra 46

6 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

2 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa

8 r. 12 q.

min maṭlūb ʿUmar Aḥmad [ʿĀwlabā] / nimra 102

6 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad

1 r. 12 q. / shuriḥa

3 r. 3 q. / shuriḥa

10 r. 15 q.

388 r. 3 q.

480 r. 18 q.

2361 r. 0 q.

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tābiʿ yawm 21 al-qaʿda 1307

2361 r. 0 q. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

480 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maṭlūbāt

388 r. 3 q. / muwāṣala

12 r. / min maṭlūb Makkī Ḥusayn / jamīʿ-hu bi-dhn wa sanad / nimra 101

49 r. / min maṭlūb ʿUmar Kisha / shuriḥa / nimra 97

24 r. / min maṭlūb Aḥmad ʿAntar / shuriḥa / nimra 53

8 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb ʿAbd Allāh Sālim / shuriḥa / nimra 3

25 r. / min maṭlūb Ḥasan Barnūs / shuriḥa / nimra 2

19 r. 6 q. / min maṭlūb ʿAbd al-Khāliq / shuriḥa / nimra 7

1 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ Danbar / munāwala Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ bi-dhni-hi / nimra 1

527 r. 9 q.

1008 r. 3 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb mabyūʿāt al-raqīq

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya min al-mutaḥaṣṣil min ‘Abd al-Qādir Badawī qīmat thaman ādamiyya mushtarā’ min raqīq bayt al-māl [tusammī] Faḍl al-Rājī [Fartāwiyya al-Ḥabash] mushallakh al-khaddayn balādī rabbā’ī min ḍimna al-hawāmil li-muqtaḍā idhn wa sanad bi-khatm amīn al-naqdiyya wa ‘alā muwajibi-him ṣadara idhināt li-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi / nimra 1 / 15

8 r.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb fuyūḍāt al-karīm

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila min madhkūrīn ‘an yad ‘Abd Allāh Muḥammad Shaykh ‘ushr raqīq wa muqaddama bi-ḥāfiẓa bi-khatmi-hi wa ‘alā maw wa ṣadara ‘alay-hā amr al-qubūl li-amīn al-naqdiyya wa waradat min-hi al-iḍāfa bi-khatmi-hi wa ‘alā mawjibi-hi ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim li-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 16

91 r. 6 q.

yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak 22 al-qa‘da

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisābat madhkūra

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila min madhkūrīn ‘an yad amr-hā al-Bashīr Aḥmad Ḥusayn wa wārīda bi-mawjib sanad iḍāfa ‘alā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya ‘uhīdat-hi wa idhn khāsm wa iḍāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi waraqa 1 / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 17

ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb madhkūrīn / jamī‘-hu ‘an-mā ukhidha min-him salafīyya / jamī‘-hu qūshlī

8 r. 6 q. / al-Shaykh Ibrāhīm Abd al-Fātiḥ thaman khām 3 ṭāqa / nimra 98

2 r. 18 q. / ‘Uthmān Bashīr al-Maṣūwa‘ī thaman khām 1 ṭāqa / nimra 46

11 r.

38 r. / ilā ḥisāb al-baḍā’ī‘ al-tijāriyya/ jamī‘-hu min al-mutaḥaṣṣil min Aḥmad ‘Abbās al-Maṣūwa‘ī ‘ushr [?]

49 r.

min ḥisābat madhkūra / min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa min madhkūrīn al-Sayyid Aḥmad amīn al-naqdiyya bi-muqtaḍā ḥāfiẓa li-khatmi-hi wa ṭayy-hā udhūnāt ‘adad 40 ‘alay-him sanad [?] al-istilām wa ‘alay-[?] dhālika ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khāsm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa ‘adad [?] al-Sayyid Aḥmad Ḥusayn / jamī‘-hu qūshlī / 18

3517 r. 9 q.

tābi‘ yawm 22 al-qa‘da 1307

3517 r. 9 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

min ḥisāb al-maṣrūf

iḥsānāt

rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

khaṣṣat al-rāyat / nimra 129

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrin [?] li-ghāya

12 q. / [?] ‘Abd al-[Ḥarsūdāt]

12 q. / [?] Muḥammad Aḥmad

1r.

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarifān li-madhkūrin

3 q. 1,5 qr. / Muṣṭafā [Barūsī]

9 q. / Nāṣir [naḥḥās]

9 q. / Faraj Allāh shuriḥa

21 q. 1,5 qr.

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarifān munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Aḥmad mulāzim wa jamā‘ati-hi luzūm ghadā’-hum

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrin

12 q. / ‘Abd al-[Nabi]

12 q. / Imān [Sālmī]

12 q. / Imān Muḥammad mulāzim

12 q. / Maḥmūd mulāzim

2 r.

4 r. 21 q. 1,5 qr.

rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb / nimra 135

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muṣṭafā Awhājj thaman kafan li-
[‘urfi]

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrin

1 r. / [?] Muḥammad Ṭāhir Mubārak thaman bunn qahwa luzūm al-
Majdhūb

1 r. / ‘Alī Ḥāmid izālat ḍarar

1 r. 3 q. / Imān ‘Abd Allāh Muḥammad Sayyid

3 r. 3 q.

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarifān ilā al-[Faqīr] ḍimna [?] bi-amr al-
Majdhūb izālat ḍarar

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad luzūm tawaṣṣuli-hi ilā al-ḥarma Amūna bint
Aḥmad / shuriḥā

1 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ‘Alī walad Muḥammad mulāzim
‘Abd Allāh Abū Bakr thaman jubba

2 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ‘Uthmān al-amīn izālat ḍarar

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarifān li-madhkūrīn adnā-hi

12 q. / Imān ʿAbd Allāh

6 q. / Ādam al-[Mankabāy]

6 q. / Ḥasan al-[Mankabāy]

1 r.

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn

6 q. / Imān ʿAbd Allāh

3 q. / [Marḥab] Allāh thaman qaşab li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh

9 q.

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā [Marḥab] Allāh al-Ḥājj thaman qaşsh li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Saʿīd [?] ʿAbd Allāh izālat ḍarar

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn

1 r. / Ḥāmid [Labībāy] izālat ḍarar

1 r. 12 q. / thaman bāb li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh Abū Bakr

2 r. 12 q.

4 r. 21 q. 1,5 qr.

18 r. 12 q.

3517 r. 9 q.

naql nimra 41

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tābiʿ yawm 22 al-qaʿda 1307

3517 r. 9 q. / muwāşala

tābiʿ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maşrūfāt

iḥsānāt

tābiʿ rāyat al-mukarram ʿUthmān Diqna

4 r. 21 q. 1,5 qr. / muwāşala

tābi rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb

18 r. 12 q. / muwāşala

3 q. 1,5 qr. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā [?] Karīm [Barūsī]

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn izālat ḍarar

12 q. / Muḥammad al-amīn

12 q. / Muḥammad Mūsā mulāzim

3 q. / ʿAbd al-Karīm

12 q. / Ṭaha Maḥmūd mulāzim

1 r. / thaman bāb khashab li-manzil ʿAbd Allāh

2 r. 18 q.

- 3 q. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Imān Bashīr
 21 r. 15 q. 1,5 qr.
 rāyat Ḥasan Musā / nimra 96
 3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Muḥammad ʿAlī Sulaymān izālat
 ðarar bi-amr al-Majdhūb
 12 q. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā ʿAbd al-Qādir [?]
 ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn thaman khām
 18 q. / Ḥasan [Maḥallāwī]
 18 q. / Maḥmūd [Jilānī]
 1 r. 12 q.
 2 r. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā ʿAḥmad Muştafā thaman jubba
 wa sarwāl
 1 r. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Khālid thaman şābūn luzūm
 Muştafā
 1 r. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Muştafā [Jilānī] izālat ðarar
 9 r.
 rāyat ʿAwd al-Karīm Kāfūt / nimra 95
 12 q. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā Aḥmad Muḥammad thaman
 kafan
 12 q. / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif Saʿīd al-Ḥājj ʿAlī / shuriḥa
 ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn izālat ðarar
 12 q. / Ḥāmid Mukhtār
 12 q. / Muḥammad Ḥamad
 12 q. / Ādam
 1 r. 12 q. / [?] Saʿīd thaman jubba
 3 r.
 4 r.
 3 r. / rāyat Mūsā ʿAlī Diqna / jamʿ-hu bi-dhn munşarif ilā ʿAbd Allāh
 Maḥmūd / nimra 3
 1 r. 15 q. / rāyat Faḍl ʿAbd Allāh / jamʿ-hu bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā
 mursāl [?] thaman [kaffa] luzūm jihati-hi / nimra 19
 12 q. / rāyat Muştafā Hadal / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā jamʿ-hu izālat
 ðarar / nimra 16
 3 q. / rāyat Aḥmad al-Majdhūb / ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif ilā
 Ibrāhīm Dusūqī / nimra 28
 44 r. 21 q.
 rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ʿUthmān Abī Qarja khāşşa
 5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munşarif ilā al-Şādiq Ṭalḥa bi-amr al-Majdhūb
 ðimna idhn wa sanad munşarif li-madhkūrīn [?] [?]
 12 q. / [ʿAjab] muqaddam [?]
 3 q. 1,5 qr. / [?] [?]
 15 q. 1,5 qr.
 5 r.
 44 r. 21 q.

3517 r. 9 q.

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tābi' yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak 22 al-qa' da 1307

3517 r. 9 q. / muwāṣala nimra 41

tābi' min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābi' min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

iḥsānāt

44 r. 21 q. / muwāṣala / nimra 41

tābi' rāyat al-mukarram Muḥamamd 'Uthmān Abī Qarja

5 r. / muwāṣala

tābi bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

15 q. 1,5 qr. / muwāṣala

[crossed]

3 q. 1,5 qr. / Allāh [?] [Barūsī]

3 q. 1,5 qr. / Ḥāmid [?]

1 r. 1,5 qr.

6 r. 1,5 qr.

rāyat Khātir Ḥamīdān

2 r. / khāṣṣat al-rāya / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā 'Isā Muḥammad izālat ḍarar bi-amr al-Majdhūb / nimra 137

15 r. / rāyat Aḥmad Sa'īd / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā 'Abd al-Raḥmān 'Abd al-Rāziq / shuriḥa / nimra 58

rāyat shuriḥa / nimra 56

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn izālat ḍarar

12 q. / Ḥājj Muḥammad

12 q. / Muḥammad Ibrāhīm

1 r.

1 r.

18 r.

rāyat al-Sayyid Muḥammad Aḥmad Idrīs / nimra 110

4 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā 'Abd al-Ḥāmid Aḥmad bi-amr al-Majdhūb

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn

12 q. / [Marr] al-[Jawāb]

9 q. / Muḥammad 'Alī

9 q. / Mūsā

1 r. 3 q.

5 r. 3 q.

3 q. / rāyat Shā'ib Aḥmad Faḍalū / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā

‘Awḍ [Barūsī] / nimra 128

rāyat Ḥamad al-Nīl / jamī‘-hu ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn [?] / nimra 68

3 q. 1,5 qr. / Mūsā [Barūsī]

3 q. 1,5 qr. / Bilāl [Ṭarsaṣī]

maṣrūfāt sā’ira

ḍuyūf / nimra 124

2 r. 18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Ḥasan [Ḥadarabī] thaman ṭāqat khām

3 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā madhkūrīn zuwwāda

2 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif bi-yad Ṭāhir Mubārak luzūm al-ḍuyūf

7 r. 18 q.

1 r. / hajjāna / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā al-Ṭāhir Mubārak luzūm qash jimāl al-hajjāna / nimra 123

aqlām sā’ira / nimra 132

1 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad Nūr thaman waraq būṣṭa wa zurūf

1 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā mandūbīn [kuswa] al-mutawaffiyīn [bi-sūq] thaman [kafāna]

12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ‘Alī ‘Abd Allāh [kuswa] [?] [muqatṭa’]

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Aḥmad [Mūsālī] nazīr [?] li-ādamiyya hamala musammān Faḍl al-Rājī [?] wa mushallakha baladī

18 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad al-amīn thaman waraq

ḍimna idhn wa sanad munṣarif li-madhkūrīn thaman kaffāna li-l-masākīn

2 r. 12 q. / bi-yad Muḥammad Aḥmad [?] / nafar 5

6 q. / bi-yad [?] [?]

2 r. 18 q.

6 r. 3 q.

8 r. 18 q.

74 r. 18 q.

3517 r. 9 q.

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tābi‘ yawm al-khamīs 22 al-qa‘da 1307

3517 r. 9 q. / muwāṣala nimra 42

tābi‘ min ḥisābāt madhkūra

tābi‘ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

iḥsānāt

74 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ al-maṣrūfāt

8 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

tābi aqlām sā’ira

6 r. 6 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ ḍimna idhn munṣarif li-madhkūrīn thaman kafāna

2 r. 18 q. / muwāṣala

12 q. / [Sayyid] Ādam min [Ḥalānqā]

3 q. / Sayyid ‘Abd al-Karīm al-Amīn

12 q. / Sayyid Mūsā Muḥammad mulāzim

12 q. / Sayyid ‘Abd al-Khayr muqaddam al-jihādiyya

12 q. / bi-yad Sayyid Muḥammad

12 q. / bi-yad Sayyid Aḥmad Karār

12 q. / bi-yad Sayyid Imān [Sālamā]

6 r.

1 r. 18 q. / ḍimna wa sanad munṣarif luzūm adawāt ḥarbiyya thaman wadak wa zayt luzūm al-midfa‘a

14 r.

22 r. 18 q.

97 r. 12 q.

mukāfa’āt

6 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh kātib al-mabyū‘āt murattabi-hi shahrī ramadān wa shawwāl 1307 / nimra 17

2 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Abū Fāṭima Abū Falīdāy amīn al-mabyū‘āt murattabi-hi / 1307 / nimra 17

5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad ‘Alī Sulaymān kātib al-nuqūd murattabi-hi shahr al-qa‘da 1307 / nimra 41

5 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Bābikar ‘Alīm kātib qalam al-raḳīq murattabi-hi shahr al-qa‘da

4 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Yūsuf Khaṭīb al-najjār murattabi-hi sharh rabī‘ awal / nimra 20

3 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muṣṭafā Jilānī li-murattabi-hi shahr shawwāl / nimra 11

ḍimna udhunāt wa sanadāt munṣarif ilā Ḥusayn al-Jilānī ḍimna murattabi-hi shahr shawwāl

1 r. 6 q. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad

1 r. / ḍimna idhn wa sanad

2 r. 3 q.

27 r. 6 q.

124 r. 18 q.

min ḥisāb al-maṭlūbāt

13 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ʿUthmān Sayyid al-Maṣūwaʿī li-l-maṭlūb al-mumlā li-hi bayt al-māl / nimra 46

10 r. 18 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ʿAbd al-ʿAzīm [Sābara] bāqī maṭlūbi-hi / nimra 68

65 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Ibrāhīm Aḥmad ʿAbd al-Fattāḥ ḍimna maṭlūb waladi-hi Muḥammad Ṣadaqa / nimra 98

13 r. 12 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā ʿUthmān [?] maṭlūbi-hi / nimra 46

35 r. 3 q. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Muḥammad ʿAbd Allāh min maṭlūbi-hi / nimra 105

16 r. / bi-dhn wa sanad munṣarif ilā Aḥmad ʿAbbās maṭlūbi-hi / nimra 75

153 r. 21 q.

278 r. 15 q.

3796 r.

naql baʿad-hu [bi-waṣl] 44

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yawm al-ahad al-mubārak 25 al-qaʿda 1307

jumla

3796 r. / muwāṣala

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-zakawāt

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila ʿand yad amīn-hā min madhkūrīn qīmat zakawāt nuqūd-hum ʿām 1307 wa wāḍiḥa bayān mufradāti-him bi-daftar al-zakawāt ṭaraf fimā-hu al-ḥijja 1306 wa li-ḍarūra idāfat al-mablagh ʿalā ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya ʿuhdat qad ṣāra al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-idāfa fi taʿrīkhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / bi-l-[?] 19

67 r.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb madhkūrīn

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-maʿkhūdhā min madhkūrīn salafīyya ʿan yad al-mukarram Majdhūb Abū Bakr naẓarān li-khalū bayt al-māl wa wārīda bi-kashf wa ʿalay-hi ifāda bi-khatmi-hi li-wakīl bayt al-māl bi-ʿitimād ʿalāwati-hā ṭalab bi-ʿismbi-sm al-madhkūr wa ʿalā [dhikr] qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-idāfa fi taʿrīkhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / bi-l-[?] 20

76 r. 12 q. / Diyāb [Fabāḍ] / nimra 83

96 r. / Aḥmad ʿAntar / nimra 53

140 r. / mutaḥaṣṣil min madhkūrīn bi-maʿrifat Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ Dunbar / nimra 1

25 r. / ‘Abd Allāh al-Ṭayyib Qamr al-Dīn thaman ādamī mubā‘ bi-ma‘rifati-hi /
nimra 60

30 r. / al-Sayyid [?] munāwala al-[?] Ḥamad / nimra 108

25 r. / Aḥmad ‘Umar Qamr al-Dīn thaman ādamī / nimra 107

150 r. / Ḥasan Barnūs / nimra 2

25 r. / ‘Abd Allāh Muḥammad Sālim / nimra 3

568 r. 12 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa li-madhkūrīn ‘an yad al-mukarram
Majdhūb Abū Bakr wa muqaddama bi-[kashf] wa ‘ala ifāda bi-khatmi bi-‘timādi
khaṣm-hā li-ḥāṣil-ḥa wa ‘alā dhālika min ‘amaliyyat ‘and al-[?] al-lāzim wa
ṣadara al-idhn bi-l-khaṣm wa al-idāfa fī ta’rīkhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī-hu
qūshlī / [?] 21

rāyāt al-mukarram ‘Uthmān

khāṣṣat rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān / nimra 129

2 r. / munṣarif fī naẓīr thaman qarb miyāh li-l-jihādiyya al-mutawajjiha
mirsāl al-dhura li-Kasalā bi-yad ‘Abd al-Khayr

3 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad Aḥmad [?] thaman qarb miyāh li-l-mulāzima

5 r. / bi-yad ‘Abd al-[Bā’in] luzūm al-jihādiyya al-muḥaddara min jihat
Kasalā [?] ‘Uthmān al-Nā’ib

5 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad Aḥmad [Tīta] madhkūrīn shuriḥa muḥaddara
min Kasalā

2 r. / li-khaṣṣat Muḥammad Aḥmad [Tīta]

1 r. / Bilāl [khudām] ḥuṣān al-‘āmil

11 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad Aḥmad [Tīta] luzūm mushtarī ‘adlib li-[?] li-
manzil al-‘āmil

5 r. / bi-yad ‘Umar Idrīs luzūm mushtarī qaṣab li-manzil al-‘āmil

34 r.

rāyat Aḥmad al-Majdhūb / nimra 28

40 r. / thaman jāriyya ma’khūdha min Ḥasan Barnūs ilā al-amīn Aḥmad
al-Majdhūb

40 r. / thaman [ḥimāra] ma’khūdha [?] ilā ‘Abd Allāh Aḥmad al-
Majdhūb

80 r.

rāyat al-Ṭāhir al-Majdhūb / nimra 136

8 r. / li-‘āmil al-Majdhūb al-Ṭāhir fī [?] murattabi-hi

7 r. / li-‘āmil al-‘ahad Yūsuf Abū Bakr

6 r. / thaman khām 2 ṭāqa luzūm jubab li-mulāzamiyya Majdhūb

1 r. / thaman kafan li-sutrat Ādam [?] Shamsī ‘Alī

1 r. / ilā Sūmīt al-Jihādī

23 r.

rāyat Khālīd al-[Makū] Nimir / nimra 140

12 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad walad al-Ḥasan al-[Makū] Nimir li-mushtarā
manāzil ilāy-hi

8 r. / bi-yad Khālīd al-[Makū] Nimir / shuriḥa qīl-hu

5 r. / bi-yad al-Nimir al-[Makū] / shuriḥa

25 r.

162 r.

naql ba‘ad-hi bi-[waṣl] 45

4373 r. 12 q.

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tābi‘ yawm al-‘ahad al-mubārak 25 al-qa‘da 1307

jumla

4373 r. 12 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt

tābi‘ rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Diqna

162 r. / muwāṣala

2 r. / rāyat al-Siddīq ‘Abd al-Wahhāb / jamī‘-hu min ṣarf ilā al-[Ṣādiq] walad
al-Ṭayyīb / nimra 141

3 r. / rāyat al-Imān [?] / jamī‘-hu muṣarif li-khāṣṣati-hi / nimra 36

1 r. 12 q. / rāyat Mūsā Aḥmad al-Sayyid / jamī‘-hu muṣarif bi-yad Aḥmad /
nimra 142

5 r. / rāyat Muḥammad walad ‘Abd Allāh / jamī‘-hu muṣarif ilā Muḥammad
walad Karam Allāh / nimra 143

40 r. / rāyat Ḥasan Mūsā / jamī‘-hu muṣarif ilā Muṣtafā al-Jilānī thaman
ḥimār / nimra 138

213 r. 12 q.

rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ‘Uthmān Abī Qarja

5 r. / khāṣṣat al-rāyat / jamī‘-hu muṣarif bi-yad Muḥammad Aḥmad al-
Shaykh Faraḥ luzūm ‘ā‘ilat Muḥammad al-Amīn ‘Ammār / nimra 133

1 r. / Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh Fāna / jamī‘-hu muṣarif ilā Abū al-Zayd
muqaddam al-[Badalqadāriyya] / nimra 122

6 r.

rāyat Khāṭir Ḥamīdan

khāṣṣat rāyat al-Ta‘ā‘isha / nimra 137

60 r. / thaman ḥimār makhūdh min Ḥasan al-[Ḥadarabi] lāzim [qadīr]

2 r. / ḥimār [ḥabāb]

62 r.

8 r. / rāyat Aḥmad [Shafa] ‘Abd al-Rāziq / jamī‘-hu muṣarif bi-yad ‘Abd al-

Raḥīm akhī-hi li-binā manzili-hi wa jamā'ati-hi / nimra 58

3 r. / rāyat walad al-Maṣūwa'ī / jamī'-hu munṣarif ilā Muṣṭafā 'Alī Hadal al-rāyat / nimra 57

6 r. / rāyat al-Barnūs / jamī'-hu munṣarif ilā Ḍaw al-[-?] Ādam thaman [-?] / nimra 56

79 r.

1 r. 12 q. / rāyat Aḥmad [Marawī] walad al-[-?] / jamī'-hu munṣarif ilā Muḥammad 'Alī 'Abd al-Raḥmān al-kātib / nimra 121

2 r. / rāyat al-Sayyid Muḥammad 'Aḥmad Shaykh Idrīs / jamī'-hu munṣarif ilā Muḥammad walad Muḥammad Aḥmad kātib al-rāya / nimra 110

2 r. / rāyat al-Sharīf Ḥamad al-Nīl Ḥāmid / jamī'-hu munṣarif ilā Sulaymān Zāyd / nimra 68

maṣrūfāt sā'ira

ḍuyūf / nimra 144

50 r. / thaman jāriyya ma'khūdhā min Ḥasan Barnūs Sulaymān ilā [-?] al-[-?] [Jirani]

40 r. / thaman [-?] ma'khūdhā ilā Yūsuf Sulaymān aḥad [-?] al-Sinn min Ḥasan al-[-?] [Ḥadarabī]

4 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad Ṭāhir Mubārakū li-maṣarif madhkūrīn ḍuyūf

94 r.

47 r. / [-?] jimāl 'adad 47 marsūla ilā Kasalā [maḥmūl] 'alay-hā zāra li-l-'āmil 'Uthmān / nimra 74

hajjāna al-būṣṭa / nimra 123

15 r. / bi-yad 'Alī Ibrāhīm wa Awnūr Ibrāhīm al-mutawajjihīn li-Kasalā

5 r. / thaman zuwwāda li-l-madhkūrīn qabli-hi

2 r. / thaman kiswa ilā 'Alī Ibrāhīm

18 r. / munṣarif li-l-hajjāna min al-Buqa'a ḍimna iqāmat-hum bi-Tūkar 'ala yad Ṭāhir Mubārakū

3 r. / bi-yad Muḥammad Karār al-ḥajjāna al-muḥaddāra min al-Buqa'a thaman makhlūfa

5 r. / thaman zuwwāda li-hajjāna al-Buqa'a Faḍl Allāh Karār wa man ma'a-hum ḥāl tawajjuh-hum Handūb

1 r. / thaman qashsh li-jimāl al-hajjāna al-muḥaddāra min al-Buqa'a

1 r. / 'Umar al-Fārūq

1 r. 12 q. / zuwwāda li-l-hajjāna al-mutawajjih Handūb

51 r. 12 q.

aqlām sā'ira / nimra 144

2 r. / [-?] bi-yad Ṭāhir Mubārakū li-madhkūrīn masākīn

4 r. / Ibrāhīm sā'ir Kasalā [-?]

5 r. / bi-yad 'Umar Aḥmad [-?] thaman jubab li-l-Ḥāmdāb al-muḥaddārīn min al-jibāl

11 r.

203 r. 12 q.

507 r. 12 q.

4373 r. 12 q.

naql ba'ad-hu bi-[waşl] 46

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tābi' yawm al-ahad al-mubarak 25 al-qa'da 1307

jumla

4373 r. 12 q. / muwāşala

tābi' min hisāb al-māşrūfāt

507 r. 12 q. / muwāşala / jamī'-hu min ihsānāt

min hisāb al-murattabāt / jamī'-hu bi-yad 'Umar Kisha ḥawāla min ṭaraf 'Abd Allāh al-Fākir / nimra 14

27 r. / bāqī murattab rabī' awal

40 r. / murattab rabī' akhar

1 r. / murattab min jumāda awal

68 r.

575 r. 12 q.

yawm al-arba' al-mubarak 28 thamāniyya wa 'ishrayn al-qa'da 1307

min hisāb ḥāşil al-naqdiyya / ilā hisāb maṭlūb al-Bashīr walad al-Nūr /

nimra 109

wa dhālika 'an al-naqdiyya al-ma'khūdhā min al-Bashīr walad al-Nūr min ahāli al-[?] bi-ḥasab ḍarūra al-lāzim li-şanf al-ghilāl 'an yad al-mukarram al-Majdhūb Abū Bakr kamā al-ifāda al-wārida min-hi bi-khatmi-hi fi-ta'rikhi-hi wa i'timād 'ilāwat al-mablagh ṭalab bi-sm al-madhkūr wa 'alā mawjibi-hi qad şadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaşm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta'rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī'-hu qūshlī / [?] 22

athmān dhura

riyāl / 'adad / fi riyāl

330 / 66 / 5

70 / 10 / 7

54 / 9 / 6

48 / 6 / 8

502 r.

ḥawālāt madhkūra

25 r. 15 q. / ḥawālat al-Ḥājj Ya'qūb

5 r. / ḥawālat al-Ḥājj Aḥmad ʿAlī

30 r. 15 q.

532 r. 15 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa li-madhkūrīn ʿan yad al-Bashīr walad al-Nūr al-muhawwal min-hum wa ʿilāwati-hā bi-sm al-Bashīr al-madhkūr ḍimna idhn fī taʾrīkhi-hi wa bināʾ ālay-hā ṣadara min al-mukarram al-Majdhūb Abū Bakr bi-ʿtimād khaṣmi-hā li-ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya bi-l-maṣrūfāt wa ʿalā mawjib ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī taʾrīkhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / nimra 23

25 r. 15 q. / rāyat al-Ḥājj Yaʿqūb al-qāʾim li-rāyat al-mukarram ʿUthmān / jamīʿ-hu ʿan al-munṣarif li-khāssati-hi / nimra 9

5 r. / rāyat Muḥammad al-Azraq / jamīʿ-hu ʿan al-munṣarif ilā Aḥmad al-Ḥājj ʿAlī / nimra 12

30 r. 15 q.

min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfāt ḥāṣil al-mushtarawāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / nimra 75

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa ilā al-Bashīr walad al-Nūr qīmat thaman dhura 91 kīs maʾkhūdhā min-hi li-munāsibat ḥuṣūl [al-iḥbāḥ] ilāy-hi li-izālat ḍarūrāt al-ikhwān alladhīna bi-l-ribāṭ wa uḍifa bi-hi li-ḥāṣil al-ghilāl bi-muqtaḍā idhn fī-taʾrīkhi-hi wa li-ḍarūrat khaṣm al-mablagh li-ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī taʾrīkhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / bi-nimra 24

502 r.

yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak 29 al-qaʿda 1307

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb al-mabyūʿāt

wa dhālika ʿan al-naqdiyya al-mutaḥaṣṣila ʿalā yad amīn al-mabyūʿāt Abū Fāṭima Abū [Falday] wa al-Ḥājj Faḍl Allāh Karār qīmat athmān mawāshī mubāʿa ʿalā yadi-him bi-l-sūq li-madhkūrīn bi-ḥisāb al-ḥāfiẓa al-wārida min-hum wa ṣāra ʿalay-hā idhn al-qubūl li-amīn al-naqdiyya wa warada-hu thaman al-iḍāfa bi-khatmi-hi ʿala mawjibi-hi sādara idhn al-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī taʾrīkhi-hi / warāqa 1 / jamīʿ-hu qūshlī / bi-nimra 25

athmān al-aghnām

75 r. / 100 ʿadad / mushtarī Ādam Idrīs wa Muḥammad Maḥmūd

62 r. / 100 ʿadad / mushtarī Muḥammad ʿAbd al-Rāziq

250 r. / 300 ʿadad / mushtarī Ibrāhīm Maḥmūd

80 r. / 100 ʿadad / mushtarī Ibrāhīm ʿAbd al-Fattāḥ

467 r. / 600 ʿadad

6014 r. 6 q.

naql ba‘ad-hu bi-[waṣl] 47

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tābi‘ yawm al-khamīs al-mubārak 29 al-qa‘da 1307

jumla

6014 r. 6 q. / muwāṣala

tābi‘ min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

tābi‘ athmān al-aghnām

467 r. / 600 ‘adad / muwāṣala

20 r. / 70 ‘adad / mushtarī Muḥammad Ḥusayn

487 r.

254 r. / athmān baqqar ‘adad 26 / mushtarī Ibrāhīm Maḥmūd

741 r.

min ḥisābāt al-madhkūra / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa li-madhkūrīn ‘an yad al-mukarram al-Majdhūb Abū Bakr Yūsuf bi-muqtaḍā kashf wa ‘alā Ifāda bi-khatmi wa ‘alā mawjibi-hi ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta’rīkhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī-hu qūshlī / 26

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt

rāyat al-mukarram ‘Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna

1 r. / rāyat Awḍ al-Karīm Kafūt / jamī‘-hu munṣarif ilā Aḥmad al-Bashīr / nimra 139

6 r. / rāyat Fādl ‘Abd Allāh / jamī‘-hu ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Ḥākim Muḥammad Khayr / nimra 19

7 r.

rāyat al-mukarram Muḥammad ‘Uthmān Abī Qarja

khāṣṣat al-rāya / nimra 133

55 r. / bi-thaman nāqa ilā Aḥmad al-Jāz li-marr-hā [jariyya] li-l-Buqa‘a al-tāhira

5 r. / ilā ‘Umar Ibrāhīm [?] [?]

3 r. / ilā mursāl [Kabūshī]

1 r. / Ḥusayn Muḥammad Khayr al-[Balqadār]

64 r.

rāyat Yūsuf al-Amīn al-Hindī / nimra 42

4 r. / Ḥājj Faḍl Allāh Karār

1 r. / ‘Abd Allāh al-[?]

1 r. / Muḥammad walad al-Ḥājj wa ‘Alī [?]

15 r. / bi-yad al-Ḥājj Faḍl Allāh li-binā’ manzil walad al-Hindī

21 r.

85 r.

35 r. / rāyat al-Ta‘ā’isha / jamī‘-hu thaman nāqa mushtarā min al-Ḥājj Khalīl al-
[?] luzūm Khāṭir Ḥamīdān ḥāl [?] li-Kasalā / nimra 137

maṣrūfāt sā’ira

60 r. / athmān jimāl / jamī‘-hu bi-thaman nāqa li-hajjāna Ḥalīm[a] al-Mahdī
‘alay-hi al-salām bi-yad Karār mushtarī / nimra 73

2 r. / aqlām sā’ira / jamī‘-hu li-madhkūrīn musā’idatīn min [rughbati]-hi wa
bay‘ al-mawāshī / nimra 144

62 r.

189 r. / yakūn **min ḥisāb al-iḥsānāt**

2 r. / **min ḥisāb al-murattabāt** / jamī‘-hu ‘an al-munṣarif ilā Abū Fāṭima Abū
[Falday] min murattabi-hi [?] / nimra 17

191 r.

550 r. / **min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-‘ahad ṭaraf Muḥammad Yūsuf** ‘an al-marsūl ilāy-
hi luzūm mushtarā ghilāl wa [taḥarrara] ‘an-hi bi-l-istaw‘āb ‘an-mā ṣarīf-hu /
nimra 13

741 r.

yawm al-jum‘a al-mubārak ghāyat al-qa‘da 1307

**min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-‘ahad al-muḥbā ṭaraf Muḥammad
Yūsuf** / nimra 13

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya qīmat al-masbūq irsāl-hā min ṭaraf al-mukarram
Majdhūb Abū Bakr ilā Muḥammad Yūsuf luzūm mushtara [?] wa [?] bi-l-‘ahad
ṭarafī-hi wa yakūn jarā [mudāraka] bi-hi al-luzūm wa muqtaḍā khaṣm li-ḥāṣil al-
‘ahad qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fī ta’rikhi-hi / waraqa
1 / jamī-hu qūshlī [?] [?] li-ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / 27

550 r.

8046 r. 6 q.

naql ba‘adi-hi bi-[waṣl] 48

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tābi‘ yawm ghāyat al-qa‘da 1307

tābi‘ jumla

8046 r. 6 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt / ilā ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya

wa dhālika ‘an al-naqdiyya al-munṣarifa fī [?] [?] li-ḍarūrat luzūm-hā min ḍimna
al-mablagh al-marsūl ilā Muḥammad Yūsuf Faḍl Allāh Karār bi-l-‘ahad ṭarafī-hi

li-ḍarūrat khaṣmi-hi qad ṣadara al-idhn al-lāzim bi-l-khaṣm wa al-iḍāfa fi ta'rikhi-hi / waraqa 1 / jamī-hu qūshlī / 28

220 r. 12 q. / mushtarawāt / jamī-hu thaman dhura 63 kīs / masbūq iḍāfat li-ḥāṣil al-ghilāl [?] / nimra 75

sā'ira rūk al-rāya / jamī-hu 'athmān jarā mushtarā-hā wa [arsala]-hu li-l-mukarram 'Uthmān Abū Bakr Diqna luzūm bi-tashīlāt al-katā'ib al-muḥaddāra min Kasalā li-ḥadd Tūkar / nimra 144

297 r. 12 q. / thaman dhura 70 kīs / 4 r. 6 q. fi riyāl

15 r. / thaman daqīq 2

11 r. / thaman tanakat saman

6 r. / thaman tanakat [zayt]

329 r. 12 q.

550 r.

8596 r. 6 q. / yakūn

0000 r. / tanzīl 'an al-muta'akhhir li-ghāyat shawwāl 1307

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-naqdiyya / jamī-hu ilā ḥisābāt madhkūra

1324 r. 3 q. / **ilā ḥisāb al-'ushr**

1413 r. 15 q. / **ilā ḥisāb al-maṭlūbāt**

749 r. / **ilā ḥisāb al-mubū'āt**

222 r. 9 q. / **ilā ḥisāb al-fuyūdāt**

550 r. / **ilā ḥisāb al-'ahad**

40 r. / **ilā ḥisāb al-zakawāt**

4299 r. 3 q.

min ḥisāb al-maṭlūbāt

337 r. / min maṭlūb Ādam Muḥammad Sālim al-Maṣūwa'ī

97 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb 'Abd al-Qādir Aḥmad Yaḥyā

10 r. / min maṭlūb Aḥmad [Mayāh]

59 r. 6 q. / min maṭlūb Ḥusayn al-Ṣāfi

55 r. 6 q. / min maṭlūb Muḥammad Sālim

26 r. / min maṭlūb Nasīm al-Ruwayḥī

121 r. / min maṭlūb Ṣāliḥ 'Abd Allāh

10 r. 15 q. / min maṭlūb 'Umar Aḥmad [Awalī]

12 r. / min maṭlūb Makkī Ḥusayn

49 r. / min maṭlūb 'Umar Kisha

24 r. / min maṭlūb Aḥmad 'Antar

8 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb 'Abd Allāh Sālim

25 r. / min maṭlūb Ḥusayn Mūsā

19 r. / min maṭlūb ʿAbd al-Khāliq
1 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ Danbar
10 r. 18 q. / min maṭlūb ʿAbd al-ʿAzam [Ṣābara]

866 r. 15 q.

4299 r. 3 q.

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jumla

4299 r. 3 q. / muwāṣala

tābiʿ min ḥisāb al-maṭlūb

866 r. 15 q. / muwāṣala

35 r. 12 q. / min maṭlūb ʿUthmān Bashīr

65 r. / min maṭlūb Ibrāhīm ʿAbd al-Fattāḥ

35 r. 3 q. / min maṭlūb Muḥammad ʿAbd ʾAllāh min rāyat walad al-Azraq

16 r. / min maṭlūb Aḥmad ʿAbbās

1018 r. 6 q.

min ḥisāb ḥāṣil al-maṣrūfāt / jamīʿ-hu ilā ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

60 r. 18 q. 1 qr. / rāyāt al-mukarram ʿUthmān Diqna

210 r. 6 q. 1,5 qr. / rāyāt al-mukarram Muḥammad ʿUthmān Abī Qarja

107 r. / rāyāt Khāṭir Ḥumaydān

2 r. 9 q. / rāyāt Ḥamad al-Nīl Ḥāmid

94 r. 18 q. 2,5 qr. / rāyāt Shāʿib Ḥamad Faḍalūl

39 r. 18 q. / rāyāt al-Sayyid Muḥammad Aḥmad

1 r. 12 q. / rāyāt Aḥmad Badawī Abū Ṣafiya

maṣrūfāt sāʿira

120 r. 9 q. 1 qr. / ḍuyūf

54 r. 12 q. / hajjāna

60 r. / athmān jimāl

74 r. / ajr jimāl

722 r. 12 q. / mushtarawāt jamīʿ-hu [bi]-ḥabb dhura 154 kīs

487 r. 15 q. / aqlām sāʿira

18 r. / al-murtajaʿāt

132 r. 18 q. / murattabāt khadamā bayt al-māl

1669 r. 18 q. 1 q.

2728 r. 21 q.

550 r. / **min ḥisāb ḥāşil al-‘ahad ṭaraf Muḥammad Yusūf / jamī‘-hu ilā ḥisāb al-naqdiyya**

8596 r. 6 q.

1324 r. 6 q. / **ilā ḥisāb al-‘ushr / jamī‘-hu ‘an badā’i‘ min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya**
ilā ḥisāb maṭlūb madhkūrīn / jamī‘-hu min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

80 r. / Muḥammad ‘Abd Allāh min rāyat Walad al-Azraq

204 r. 12 q. / Aḥmad al-Şāliḥ

18 r. / Muḥammad Abī al-Makkī Şāliḥ

8 r. 6 q. / al-Shaykh Ibrāhīm ‘Abd al-Fattāh

2 r. 18 q. / ‘Uthmān Bashīr

76 r. 12 q. / Diyāb [Fabāş]

96 r. / Aḥmad ‘Antar

140 r. / maṭlūb madhkūrī munāwala Muḥammad Şāliḥ Danbar

25 r. / ‘Abd Allāh al-Ṭayyib

30 r. / Sayyid [?]

25 r. / Aḥmad ‘Umar Qamr al-Dīn

150 r. / Ḥasan Barnūs

25 r. / ‘Abd Allāh Sālim

532 r. 15 q. / al-Sayyid walad al-Nūr

1413 r. 15 q.

2737 r. 18 q.

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2737 r. 18 q. / muwāşala

ilā ḥisāb al-mabyū‘āt

741 r. / mabyū‘āt al-mawāşhī

8 r. / mabyū‘āt al-raqīq

749 r.

ilā ḥisāb al-fuyūḍāt / jamī‘-hu min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya

131 r. 3 q. / mutaḥaşşil musā‘aida bi-madhkūrīn wāridīn wa [mutariddīn] min wa ilā Tūkar wa Trinkitāt

91 r. 6 q. / mutaḥaşşil bi-madhkūra musā‘ada min tadāwul qalam al-raqīq

222 r. 9 q.

550 r. / **ilā ḥisāb al-‘ahad ṭaraf Muḥammad Yūsuf / jamī‘-hu min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya**

40 r. / **ilā ḥisāb al-zakawāt naqdiyya / jamī‘-hu min ḥisāb al-naqdiyya**

ilā ḥisāb al-naqdiyya / jamī^ʿ-hu min ḥisābāt madhkūrīn

1018 r. 6 q. / **min ḥisāb al-maṭlūb**

550 r. / **min ḥisāb al-ʿahad**

2728 r. 21 q. / **min ḥisāb al-maṣrūfat**

4697 r. 3 q.

8596 r. 6 q.

faqaṭ wa qadra-hu thamāniya ālāf wa khamsamāya wa sitta wa tisa^ʿūn riyāl wa rub^ʿ
min riyāl lā ghayr ziyāda